

The Relationship between Plasma Homocysteine Levels and Diabetic Complications in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

Mohammad Amzarul¹, Ravi Kishore Reddy Vintha², Mohammad Tahazzul³, Samreen Farooqui⁴, Deepti Gangwar⁵, Sara Siddiqui⁶

¹Consultant Physician, Lucknow, India

²Dean Academics at Saint Martinus University Faculty of Medicine, Curacao

³Assistant Professor Dept of Pediatrics T. S. M Medical college, Lucknow

⁴Assistant Prof Dept of Physiology Jazan university .K.S.A

⁵Assistant Prof Dept of pathology IIMSR, Lucknow, India

⁶Assistant Prof Dept of Physiology IIMSR, Lucknow, India

Received: 20-04-2023 / Revised: 19-05-2023 / Accepted: 20-06-2023

Corresponding author: Dr Sara Siddiqui

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Patients with Diabetes Mellitus have 2- to 6-fold increase in the prevalence of cardiovascular disease (CVD) as compared to non-DM subjects. Epidemiological data has shown that DM is synergic with other conventional risk factors. Total plasma homocysteine (tHcy) is an emerging CVD risk factor. We did a cross-sectional study to explore the relationship between tHcy and CVD in patients with DM.

Methods: The present study was conducted in department of medicine in collaboration with department of Physiology in IIMSR for a period of one year from June 2022 to May 2023. A total number of 316 diabetic patients between age group 25-65 years were enrolled from the diabetic clinic and those admitted in the Department of Medicine IIMSR who satisfied the selection criteria (n=316)..

Results: Out of 316 diabetic patients, 197 have duration of diabetes less than 5 years, out of these 116 (58.9%) had normal and 81 (41.12%) had raised plasma Homocysteine level. 108 diabetic patients had duration between 5 to 10 years, out of these 46 (42.59%) patients had normal and 62 (57.4%) patients had raised plasma Homocysteine level which was statistically significant ($\chi^2=1.91$, $p=0.019$). 11 patients had duration more than 10 year So, majority of diabetic patients who had raised plasma Homocysteine level had duration between 5 to 10 years. Out of 316 diabetic patients, 26 (8.2%) patients had stroke and 24 (7.5%) had coronary artery disease. These patients had significant elevation of plasma homocysteine level as compared to those patients who had no evidence of cerebrovascular or cardiovascular disease ($p<0.001$). homocysteine level.

Conclusions: This study concludes plasma homocysteine level can be considered as an early marker, It can be concluded from our study that diabetic patients who had elevated homocysteine level have more complications in the form of nephropathy, neuropathy, retinopathy and higher incidence of cerebrovascular disease and ischemic heart disease as compared to those diabetic patients who had normal plasma homocysteine level. We also recommend for routine screening of plasma homocysteine level for purpose of treating elevated homocysteine concentrations in the wider adult populations.

Key words: Total plasma homocysteine, Coronary artery disease, Nephropathy, Ischemic Heart Disease.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative

(<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a highly prevalent metabolic disease and is a major global health problem. Prevalence of diabetes has tripled since 1970. The number of cases of diabetes mellitus World Wide in 2000 among adult of >20 years of age is estimated to be 171 million. The prevalence of diabetes for all age group worldwide was 2.8% in 2000 and estimated to be 4.4% in 2030[1].

In India >40 million people have diabetes mellitus. The crude prevalence rate of diabetes is estimated to be around 9% in urban areas and 3% in rural areas. [2]. Homocysteine (Hcy) is the transmethylation product of the essential sulphur-containing amino acid methionine. Experiments have shown that high concentrations of homocysteine may cause vascular Epidemiological research suggests an association between elevated total homocysteine (tHcy) levels and cardiovascular disease (CVD), which is the most common cause of mortality in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus [3]. The association between homocysteinemia and atherosclerotic vascular disease is especially strong in patients with type 2 diabetes, compared to nondiabetic subjects. Increased plasma tHcy levels are reported to be associated with hypertension, hyperlipidemia, smoking, hyperuricemia, and impaired adrenal function. Plasma tHcy concentration is strongly related to renal function. A study in rats identified the kidney as a major site for removal and metabolism of Hcy. Two mechanisms appear to be involved. The main source of Hcy is adenosylmethionine-dependent methylation of guanidoacetate to form creatine and its anhydride creatinine. Second, renal function plays a central role for clearance of both creatinine and Hcy[4]. Growing interest is being focused on the association of homocysteinemia with

diabetes mellitus. However, consensus on how type 2 diabetes affects plasma homocysteine concentrations has not been achieved. Homocysteinemia has been established as a risk factor for cardiovascular disease and occurs with high prevalence in patients with type 2 diabetes: 31% of type 2 diabetic patients have homocysteine concentrations above >15 mmol/L. Only a few studies found no significant differences in fasting plasma tHcy levels between type 2 diabetic patients without microalbuminuria and healthy control subjects. A large amount of evidence supports increased plasma tHcy levels in type 2 diabetes [5].

Material and methods:

The present study was conducted in department of medicine in collaboration with department of Physiology in IIMSR for a period of one year from June 2022 to May 2023. A total number of 316 diabetic patients between age group 25-65 years were enrolled from the diabetic clinic and those admitted in the Department of Medicine IIMSR who satisfied the selection criteria (n=316). Diabetic patients who were enrolled were non-smokers, doesn't have vitamin B12 deficiency or hypothyroidism, non-hypertensive, not on antifolate drugs, and does not have established chronic kidney disease.

The information collected and observations made during the study are presented below.

Mean age of the diabetic patients (n=316) is 52.12 years. Mean age of the male patients were 53.76 years and of the female patients were 50.51 years. Male: Female ratio of the diabetic patients were 1.65:1.

Results

Demographic Profile Of The Study Group And Its Correlation With Plasma Homocysteine:

Table 1: Homocysteine level in selected diabetic patients according to age distribution

Age (years)	Normal Hcy.		Abnormal Hcy.		Total	'p' value
	No.	%	No.	%		
25-35	8	80	2	20	10	0.11
35-45	19	38.8	30	61.2	49	0.065
45-55	75	61.98	46	38.02	121	0.13
55-65	67	49.26	69	50.73	136	0.41

Figure 1:

Out of 316 diabetic patients in the study group, majority of patients are above the age of 45 years, 59 (18.6%) patients were below the age of 45 years whereas 257 (81.32%) patients were above 45 years. Patients between the age group between 35-45 years have significant elevation of

plasma homocysteine level as compared to other age group. Out of 49 patients in this age, 30 (61.2%) have elevated plasma homocysteine level as compared to 19 (38.8%) who have normal homocysteine level, which was statistically significant ($p=0.009$, $\chi^2=11.5$).

Table-2: Homocysteine level in selected diabetic patients according to duration of Diabetes

Duration (years)	Normal Hcy.		Abnormal Hcy.		Total	'p' value
	No.	%	No.	%		
<5	116	58.9	81	41.12	197	0.23
5-10	46	42.59	62	57.40	108	0.58
>10	7	63.63	4	36.36	11	0.55

Figure 2:

Out of 316 diabetic patients, 197 have duration of diabetes less than 5 years, out of these 116 (58.9%) had normal and 81 (41.12%) had raised plasma Homocysteine level. 108 diabetic patients had duration between 5 to 10 years, out of these 46 (42.59%) patients had normal and 62

(57.4%) patients had raised plasma Homocysteine level which was statistically significant ($\chi^2=1.91, p=0.019$). 11 patients had duration more than 10 years. So, majority of diabetic patients who had raised plasma Homocysteine level had duration between 5 to 10 years.

Table 3: Homocysteine level in selected diabetic patients according to serum triglyceride level

Triglyceride (mg/dl)	Normal Hcy.		Abnormal Hcy.		Total	'p' value
	No.	%	No.	%		
<150	99	63.06	58	36.94	157	0.045
>150	70	45.74	89	54.26	129	0.052

Figure 3

Out of 316 diabetic patients, 157 patients had normal triglyceride level (<150 mg/dl). Out of this 99 (63.06%) had normal and 58 (36.94%) had raised plasma Homocysteine level. 129 diabetic patients had raised

triglyceride (>150 mg/dl) out of which 89 (54.26%) had raised and 70 (45.74%) had normal plasma Homocysteine level which was found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2=11.50, p=0.001$).

Table 4: Homocysteine level in selected diabetic patients according to HDL cholesterol level

HDL (mg/dl)	Normal Hcy.		Abnormal Hcy.		Total	'p' value
	No.	%	No.	%		
Normal	84	52.5	76	47.5	160	0.84
Abnormal	85	54.49	71	45.51	156	0.84

Figure 4:

Discussion

Out of 316 diabetic patients, 160 had normal HDL level out of which 84 (52.5%) had normal and 76 (47.5%) had raised plasma Homocysteine level. 156 diabetic patients had low HDL level out of which 85 (54.49%) had normal and 71 (45.51%) had raised plasma Homocysteine level. No correlation was found between plasma LDL and Homocysteine level ($\chi^2=0.13, p=0.72$).

Out of 316 diabetic patients in the study group, majority of patients was above the age of 45 years. 59 (18.6%) patients were below the age of 45 years whereas 257 (81.32%) patients were above the age of 45 years. Patients between the age group between 35-45 years have significant elevation of plasma homocysteine level as

compared to other age group. Out of 49 patients in the age group between 35-45, 30 (61.2%) patients had elevated plasma Homocysteine level as compared to 19 (38.8%) patients who had normal level which was statistically significant ($\chi^2=11.57, p=0.009$). Although previous studies did not find any significant relationship between plasma homocysteine level and age of diabetic patients. In a study conducted by Jose Miguel Gonzalez Clemente et al in which they enrolled 93 diabetic patients with microalbuminuria in which they did not find any correlation between age of diabetic patients and plasma homocysteine level. Another study conducted by Lamia Borazines et al in 2008 in which they enrolled 168 diabetic patients with retinopathy and they also did not find

any significant correlation between plasma homocysteine level and age of diabetic patients. Though the sample size of the patients in our study in between the age group of 35-45 years was small (49 patients), homocysteine level was found to be elevated significantly. Further larger studies will be required in the near future to find some more definitive results.

In our study, out of 316 diabetic patients, majority of patients had duration of diabetes less than 5 years, however, significant correlation between plasma Homocysteine level and diabetic patients was found who had duration between 5-10 years. Out of 108 (34.17%) diabetic patients between this age group, 62 (57.40%) had raised plasma Homocysteine level as compared to 46 (42.59%) who had normal level which was found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2=7.91$, $p=0.019$). A study conducted by Ilhan Tarkun et al in 2003 in which 38 diabetic patients were enrolled found no significant correlation between plasma Homocysteine level and duration of diabetes mellitus. Laima Brajionis et al conducted a study in which 168 patients were enrolled found no significant correlation between plasma Homocysteine level and duration of diabetes mellitus. In our study, a significant correlation was found between plasma Homocysteine level and elevated cholesterol and triglyceride level. Out of 316 diabetic patients, 44 (13.92%) patients had elevated cholesterol level ($>200\text{mg/dl}$). Out of these 44 patients, 28 (63.34%) patients had elevated plasma Homocysteine level while 16 (36.36%) patients had normal level which was found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2=6.02$, $p=0.014$). 272 diabetic patients had normal cholesterol level. 129 (40.82%) diabetic patients out of 316 patients had elevated serum triglyceride level ($>150\text{mg/dl}$). Out of these 129 patients, 89 (54.26%) patients had raised plasma Homocysteine level as compared to 70 (45.74%) patients who had normal Homocysteine level which was

found to statistically significant ($\chi^2=11.50$, $p=0.001$). 157 patients had normal triglyceride level. Previous studies did not show any significant correlation between the plasma Homocysteine level and diabetic dyslipidemia. In the study conducted by Marie Jose J. Pouwels et al in 2008 found no significant correlation between elevated total cholesterol, triglyceride level and plasma Homocysteine level in diabetic patients. No significant correlation was found between plasma Homocysteine level and HDL, and LDL cholesterol level in our study

Conclusion

A significant correlation was found between plasma homocysteine and diabetic patients having duration between 5-10 years. 62 (57.40%) patients out of 108 patients had elevated plasma homocysteine level as compared to 46 (42.59%) patients who had normal homocysteine level ($p=0$). Those diabetic patients who had raised cholesterol and Triglyceride level had significant elevation of plasma homocysteine level ($p=0.001$) but no correlation was found with LDL and HDL cholesterol level. Out of 316 diabetic patients, 26 (8.2%) patients had stroke and 24 (7.5%) had coronary artery disease. These patients had significant elevation of plasma homocysteine level as compared to those patients who had no evidence of cerebrovascular or cardiovascular disease ($p<0.001$). homocysteine level. Thus, plasma homocysteine level can be considered as an early marker. It can be concluded from our study that diabetic patients who had elevated homocysteine level have more complications in the form of nephropathy, neuropathy, retinopathy and higher incidence of cerebrovascular disease and ischemic heart disease as compared to those diabetic patients who had normal plasma homocysteine level. Complications were also found in those diabetic patients who had normoalbuminuria but elevated plasma homocysteine level. Thus, plasma

homocysteine level can be considered as an early marker of progression of diabetes and its complications. We also recommend for routine screening of plasma homocysteine level for purpose of treating elevated homocysteine concentrations in the wider adult populations

References

1. Mobasseri M, Shirmohammadi M, Amiri T, Vahed N, Hosseini Fard H, Ghojzadeh M. Prevalence and incidence of type 1 diabetes in the world: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Health Promot Perspect*. 2020 Mar 30;10(2):98-115. doi: 10.34172/hpp.2020.18. PMID: 32296622; PMCID: PMC7146037.
2. Pradeepa R, Mohan V. Epidemiology of type 2 diabetes in India. *Indian J Ophthalmol*. 2021 Nov;69(11):2932-2938. doi: 10.4103/ijo.IJO_1627_21. PMID: 34708726; PMCID: PMC8725109.
3. Platt DE, Hariri E, Salameh P, Merhi M, Sabbah N, Helou M, Mouzaya F, Nemer R, Al-Sarraj Y, El-Shanti H, Abchee AB, Zalloua PA. Type II diabetes mellitus and hyperhomocysteinemia: a complex interaction. *Diabetol Metab Syndr*. 2017 Mar 21; 9:19. doi: 10.1186/s13098-017-0218-0. PMID: 28331553; PMCID: PMC5359933.
4. Levi A, Cohen E, Levi to metabolic parameters and diabetic complications. *Turkish Journal of endocrinology and metabolism* (2003) 1:11-17.
5. Castro R, Rivera I, Blom HJ, Jakobs C, De Almeida IT. Homocysteine metabolism, hyperhomocysteinemia and vascular disease: an overview. *Journal of Inherited Metabolic Disease: Official Journal of the Society for the Study of Inborn Errors of Metabolism*. 2006 Feb;29(1):3-20.
6. Laima Brazionis, Colin Alexander Harper, Kevin Rowley, Kerin O'Dea, Catherine Itsiopoulos. Homocysteine and diabetic retinopathy. *Diabetes Care* 31; 50-56, 2008.
7. Marie-Jose Pouwels, Martin den Heijer, Henk J. Blom, Cees J. Tack, Ad R. Hermus. Improved insulin sensitivity and metabolic control in type 2 diabetes mellitus does not influence plasma Homocysteine. *Diabetes Journal*, 2007; 245-48.
8. M, Goldberg E, Garty M, Krause I. Elevated serum homocysteine is a predictor of accelerated decline in renal function and chronic kidney disease: A historical prospective study. *Eur J Intern Med*. 2014 Dec;25(10):951-5. doi: 10.1016/j.ejim.2014.10.014. Epub 2014 Oct 27. PMID: 25457436.
9. Castro R, Rivera I, Blom HJ, Jakobs C, De Almeida IT. Homocysteine metabolism, hyperhomocysteinemia and vascular disease: an overview. *Journal of Inherited Metabolic Disease: Official Journal of the Society for the Study of Inborn Errors of Metabolism*. 2006 Feb;29(1):3-20.
10. Jose- Miguel Gonzalez-Clemente, Ramon Deulfeu, Jon Mitjavila, Gloria Galdon, Emilio Ortega, Assumpta Calxas, Gabriel Gimenez-peraz, Didac Mauricio. Plasma homocysteine level in microalbuminuric patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus without cardiovascular disease.
11. Ilhan Takun, Berrin C, Arslan Zeynep Canturk Pinar Turkun Guliz Kozdag Pinar Topsever. Homocysteine concentrations in type 2 Diabetes Mellitus patients without cardiovascular disease; Relationship.